

Molecular Adsorption and Ion-Exchange of Carboxylic Acids by Anion-Exchange Resin

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Molecular adsorption and ion-exchange of the carboxylic fatty acids (formic to n-butyric) by the anion-exchange resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, in its chloride and bromide forms, have been investigated. The adsorption increases in the order, formic < acetic < propionic < n-butyric. The order of ion-exchange by the two forms of the resin is found to be: Cl-resin: propionic < acetic < n-butyric < formic. Br-resin: acetic < propionic < n-butyric < formic. It is found that both adsorption and ion-exchange of the four acids are always greater with the chloride form than with the bromide form of the resin.

CARBOXYLIC fatty acids undergo molecular adsorption and ion-exchange simultaneously, when their solutions are equilibrated with the resin containing counter-ions different from that present in the resin. In the case of cation-exchange resin, H⁺ ion of the weak organic acid is exchanged with the counter-ion of the resin. In anion-exchange resin, carboxylate ion of the acid is exchanged for the counter-ion different from the carboxylate ion. Devydov and Lisovina¹, while working with organic fatty acids, obtained "super adsorption" of these acids by weak-base anion-exchange resins. They did not differentiate between molecular adsorption and ion-exchange. Starobinets and Gleim², for the first time, differentiated between molecular adsorption and ion-exchange of weak organic acids (C₁ to C₉) by an anion-exchange resin. Ermolenko and Sviridova³ obtained both molecular adsorption and ion-exchange of fumaric and maleic acids by anion-exchange resins.

In this paper, the results of a study on simultaneous molecular adsorption and ion-exchange properties of weak organic acids (formic to n-butyric) by an anion-exchange resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, in its chloride and bromide forms, are presented.

Experimental

Commercially obtained monofunctional highly basic anion-exchange resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, in chloride form was first converted to hydroxyl form by treating the resin with 0.5 N sodium hydroxide solution. The OH-resin was washed thoroughly with double distilled water to remove Cl⁻ and Na⁺ ions and other ions which were originally present in the resin.

The OH-resin was then converted to chloride and bromide forms on repeated treatment with about 1N HCl and 1N KBr solutions respectively. The chloride and bromide resins, thus obtained, were washed with double distilled water to remove excess HCl and KBr. The washed resins were then dried in air and kept in a closed container.

Formic, acetic, propionic and n-butyric acids were of purely "Analar grades" and so used without further purification.

The total exchange capacity of the resin was 2.52 ± 0.02 meq/gm. dry resin. Weighed amounts (about 1 gm) of the resin of known moisture content were taken in well stoppered Jena glass bottles. These were then shaken with acid solutions (50 ml each) of known concentrations by a mechanical shaker for 4 hours. After attainment of equilibrium, the equilibrium concentrations of the acids and Cl⁻ or Br⁻ ion in the solutions were estimated by means of suitable analytical methods.

The initial and final concentrations of the acids were found out by alkalimetric titration. The concentrations of chloride and bromide ions were estimated in separate aliquots by titrating with standard silver nitrate solution using fluorescein adsorption indicator⁴. From the concentrations of chloride and bromide ions, ion-exchanges of these ions were calculated. The molecular adsorption of the acid was calculated from the difference between initial and final concentration of the acid.

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All the experiments were done in room temperatures ($30 \pm 2^\circ$).

Results and Discussions

Molecular adsorption and ion-exchange isotherms of carboxylic acids on the chloride and bromide forms are presented graphically in figures 1a, 1b, 2a and 2b respectively. Both adsorption and ion-exchange increase with equilibrium concentrations of the acids. As expected, the adsorption is found to be increased with the chainlength of the carboxylic acids. The order of ion-exchange by the two salt forms of the resin is,

- Cl-resin : propionic < acetic < n-butyric < formic.
- Br-resin : acetic < propionic < n-butyric < formic.

Fig. 1.a) Exchange Isotherms of Carboxylic acids on the Chloride form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

Fig. 1.b) Adsorption isotherms of Carboxylic acids on the Chloride form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

Fig. 2.a) Exchange Isotherms of Carboxylic acids on the Bromide form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

Fig. 2.b) Adsorption Isotherms of Carboxylic acids on the Bromide form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

Formic acid has the largest dissociation constant among the all four carboxylic acids studied and so the ion-exchange with this acid is also highest. But with the other acids, not only the dissociation constant but also the chainlength play an important part in ion-exchange. The increasing chainlength increases the hydrophobic nature of the carboxylate ions and consequently the increase in selectivity for these ions is due to the hydrophobic interactions with the resin^{5,6}.

It is observed that for all the four carboxylic acids ion-exchange is always greater with the chloride form of the resin than with the bromide form. Similar is the case with molecular adsorption. As the selectivity of Br⁻ ion is more than Cl⁻ ion by the anion-exchange resin, the molecular adsorption as well as ion-exchange is smaller in bromide form than in chloride form of the resin. Starobinets and Gleim² showed that stronger is the electrostatic interaction between the ion fixed and the opposite ion, the weaker is the carboxylate groups attracted by the resin matrix and consequently the

molecular adsorption is smaller. But the effect of electrostatic interaction on the molecular adsorption is not always the main factor. If we compare the molecular adsorption of a particular acid by all the salt forms of the anion-exchange resin, presented here and in our previous paper⁷, following results can be obtained.

<i>Acids</i>	<i>Adsorption</i>
Formic :	$RNO_3 < RCl \approx RBr$ $< HCOOR < R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$.
Acetic :	$RBr < RCl < RNO_3$ $< CH_3COOR \approx R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$.
Propionic :	$RBr < RCl < RNO_3$ $< CH_3CH_2COOR \approx R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$.
n-butyric :	$RBr < RCl < RNO_3$ $< R_2SO_4 < CH_3CH_2CH_2COOR < R_2CrO_4$.

R = Resin matrix.

The order of the selectivity of the anions for the anion-exchange resin is⁸,

From the selectivity order, it is found that SO_4^{2-} ion has the largest selectivity among other ions given here. It has already been mentioned in our previous communications⁷ that due to site sharing⁸ acids are adsorbed strongly by the sulphate and chromate forms of the resin.

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